

A One-pot Synthesis of 4,6-Androstadien-6,17 β -diol-3-one[#]

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A new convenient one-pot synthesis of 4,6-androstadien-6,17 β -diol-3-one (3) from various steroidal enones are described.

While studying effect of the site of conjugation of a carrier protein like bovine serum albumin on testosterone (1), the nature of linkage and stereochemistry of the hapten on the specificity of antisera, we attempted to introduce a suitable functional group at C-2 of 1 using strong base in a polar solvent. During the course of this reaction, the formation of an unusual product 4,6-androstadien-6,17 β -diol-3-one (3) was observed. As 3 has been previously synthesised¹⁻⁴ in multi-step sequences in extremely low yield, it was of great interest to explore this new one-step transformation of 1 to 3 and to study the scope of this reaction.

Results and Discussion

The scope of this reaction was studied using other testosterone derivatives such as 5-androsten-17 β -ol-3-one (2), 4-androsten-3,6-dione-17 β -acetate (5)^{1,4}, 4-androsten-6 β -ol-17 β -acetoxy-3-one (6)² and 4-androsten-6 β ,17 β -diol-3-one (7)². Substrates 5 and 6 were prepared by known method from testosterone (1) which on treatment with acetic anhydride and acetyl chloride afforded 3,5-androstadien-3,17 β -diacetate⁴ followed by epoxidation with monopero-phthalic acid² gave the corresponding intermediate of 5 α ,6 α -oxido-3-androsten-3,17 β -diacetate which on treatment with saturated sodium carbonate afforded 4-androsten-6 β -hydroxy-17 β -acetoxy-3-one (5)² followed by oxidation with chromium trioxide in acetone to 4-androsten-3,6-dione-17 β -acetate (6). All the above substrates when subjected to reaction conditions gave 3 in good yields (Table 1). The reaction is highly solvent- and base-dependent. The higher molar ratio of the base and polar solvents like DMSO and MeOH tends to favor the reaction and consequently yields were also increased.

The predicted intermediate 6 may be occurring by the reaction of 1 with strong base in polar protic or aprotic solvent. This involves abstraction of the proton at allylic position (C-6) resulting in a carbanion which isomerized to 2 or 3,5-androstadien-3,17 β -diol intermediate *in situ* followed by either an electrophilic substitution at C-6 position with oxonium ion or an epoxidation occurred with molecular oxygen at C₅=C₆ double bond followed by epoxide ring-opening. The proposed intermediate 6 may be further oxidized with strong base in polar protic or aprotic solvents to give 3 as Clarke *et al.*² reported for the synthesis of 2,17 β -dihydroxyandrosta-1,4-dien-3-one from 2 β -hydroxy-testosterone using base/O₂/polar solvent. The authors did not comment on the unexpected oxidation level of their products. The formation of 3 may have occurred at allylic position of the substrates by autoxidation^{5,6} in alkaline media using polar aprotic/protic solvents as well as 2 could be understood in terms of isomerization of 1 proceeding via π -bond migration from Δ^4 - to Δ^5 -isomer.

- 1; R' = H, R = β -OH
5; R' = O; R = β -OAc
6; R' = H, β -OH; R = β -OAc
7; R' = H, β -OH; R = β -OH

- 3; R' = OH; R = β -OH
4; R' = OAc; R = β -OAc

TABLE 1—FORMATION OF 3 FROM DIFFERENT SUBSTRATES

Substrate (mmol)	Solvent (ml)	Base (eqv)	Time (h)	Product 3 % yield*
1 (1)	DMSO (10)	NaH (1.5)	4	21
	MeOH (10)	KOH (3.5)	4	48
2 (1)	MeOH (5)	KOH (1.5)	2	32
	DMF (5)	NaH (1.5)	3	26
5 (1)	DMSO (5)	NaH (1.5)	3	28
	DMSO (5)	NaH (3.5)	4	66
6 (1)	MeOH (4)	KOH (1.5)	2	68
	DMSO (5)	NaH (3.5)	3	65
7 (1)	DMSO (5)	NaH (3.5)	3	62
1 (4)	Benzene (10)	NaH (3.5)	4	No reaction

* Yield based on reagent.

is relatively long-lived (because the solvent has no proton to donate) and symmetrically solvated. Therefore the result of the product **3** in other solvent such as benzene suggests that the feasibility of the reaction is determined by the basicity of the medium and no reaction was observed in benzene solvent (Table 1). Solvents can influence the mechanism which is preferred. As with electrophilic substitution, an increase in solvent polarity increases the possibility of an ionizing mechanism.

This single-step conversion of **1** and its derivatives to **3** offers many advantages over the reported method. In the present work not only the steroidal enones have been effectively transformed to **3** but also the synthesis of product **3** was achieved in a novel manner from the various substrates in different polar solvent using different strong base (Table 1) in good yields. In all cases, the work-up of the product mixture was extremely simple and effective to isolate the product. The benefits of this type of methodology both at a laboratory scale and at an industrial scale are obvious.

To conclude, an attractive feature of this reaction is its property of effecting enolization at allylic centre (C-6) to give the corresponding product **3** which was isolated for the first time by a simplified, one-pot preparation directly from steroidal enones.

Experimental

In a typical reaction, a solution **1** (0.288 g, 1 mmol) was added dropwise to a magnetically stirred solution of KOH (0.196 g, 3.5 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) at room temperature 25–30°. The reaction was monitored by tlc disappearance of **1**. The reaction mixture was poured onto

crushed ice + HCl (pH 2), and extracted with ether, washed with saturated NaHCO₃, and dried over sodium sulfate. The solvent was evaporated and the crude residue was chromatographed over silica gel column. The product **3** was eluted using benzene-ethyl acetate (7 : 3) as eluant. Acetylation of **3** with acetic anhydride and pyridine gave the corresponding product **4**, that was identical to the product obtained by literature procedure¹ : **3**, m.p. 179–80°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3500 (OH), 1670 cm⁻¹ (conjugated C=O) δ (CDCl₃) 3.65 (1H, t, C₁₇-H), 5.85 (1H, s, C₄-H), 6.15 (1H, s, C₆-H); m/z 302 (M⁺); **4**, m.p. 187–89° (lit.¹ 191°) (Found : C, 71.52; H, 7.91. C₂₃H₃₀O₅ calcd. for : C, 71.50; H, 7.77%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1760 (C₁₇-acetate), 1720 (C₆-acetate), 1660 (conjugated C=O), 1620 (C₄=C₅), 1580 cm⁻¹ (C₆=C₇); δ (CDCl₃) 2.10 (3H, s, C₁₇-OCOCH₃), 2.20 (3H, s, C₆-OCOCH₃), 4.65 (1H, t, C₁₇-H), 5.75 (2H, s, C₄-H and C₆-H); m/z 386 (M⁺).

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